

PUBLIC SECTOR AUDIT AND ACCOUNTABILITY OF FEDERAL GOVERNMENT MINISTRIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study investigated the relationship between public sector audit and accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria with its specific objectives such as to determine the relationship between public sector audit dimensions and financial accountability, administrative accountability and social accountability. A well-structured questionnaire was developed and administered on the 26 Federal Ministries of Nigeria to facilitate the generation of primary data for the study. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was also used with aid of statistical package for social sciences version 23.0 to test the null hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that financial audit has a positive relationship with financial accountability, administrative accountability, and social accountability, compliance audit has significant relationship with financial accountability, administrative accountability and social accountability, while performance audit has a significance relationship with financial accountability. The study further indicates that auditing standards significantly moderate the relationship between public sector audit and accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria. The study therefore, recommends that there should be persistent use of financial audit, compliance audit and performance audit in federal government ministries to ensure public accountability. Public sector administrators should ensure that financial audit, compliance audit, and performance audit are done annually as a means of providing financial, administrative and social accountability of public sector entities. Finally, the government should employ more qualified audit personnel and equip them with necessary working materials, training so that they can improve their efficiency.*

1. Introduction

Unlike the private sector, which is often more responsive to stakeholder expectations, the public sector in many countries, including

Nigeria, has consistently fallen short of meeting citizens' and governments' expectations (Van der Wal et al., 2008). As Döring (1995) notes, governments are required to mobilize, allocate,

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and utilize resources responsibly and appropriately, reflecting the principal-agent relationship where citizens act as principals and public officials serve as agents (Nwaobia et al., 2021). However, the misuse of public funds, rising incidences of white-collar crime, and pervasive corruption have undermined the sector, with financial crimes becoming a major factor threatening Nigeria's economic stability and statehood (Obuah, 2010). Although the primary role of public sector auditing is to review financial records and assess whether they fairly represent the state of the economy, the current decline in transparency and accountability raises concerns about the effectiveness of this mandate. Despite being constitutionally entrenched as a mechanism for promoting accountability and transparency, public sector auditing in Nigeria has been weakened and, in many instances, relegated to a mere formality by public officeholders. Against this backdrop, this study seeks to examine the relationship between public sector audit and accountability in Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The growing global demand for transparency in governance and the widespread condemnation of wasteful expenditures, inefficiency, and corruption have made accountability a central concern in public sector management (Udeh & Elom, 2016). In Nigeria, lack of transparency and accountability remains a critical challenge, creating avenues for corruption and economic

waste (Addison, 2008). The 1999 Constitution underscores the importance of accountability by establishing the Office of the Auditor-General of the Federation to ensure executive accountability to the legislature in the administration of government activities, while the Audit Act of 1958 mandates timely submission of financial statements for legislative review. Similar accountability structures exist at the state level through Public Accounts Committees and state audit institutions. As Vijayakumar and Nagaraja (2012) note, effective public sector audits enhance efficiency, reduce overheads, safeguard assets, and strengthen financial control, thereby promoting sound management of public funds. However, despite these frameworks, misappropriation, misallocation, and embezzlement of public resources persist, raising concerns about whether audits in Nigeria's public sector effectively promote accountability. Existing empirical studies have produced mixed results, often differing in population focus, variable operationalization, or analytical methods (Onowu & Azali, 2025). To address these gaps, this study investigates the relationship between public sector audit and accountability in Nigerian public sector organizations, using robust constructs and dimensions to provide clearer insights.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between public sector audit and

accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Determine the relationship between financial audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria.
2. Examine the relationship between compliance audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria.
3. Investigate the relationship between performance audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated for this study:

1. What is the relationship between financial audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between compliance audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between performance audit on financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

With due consideration to the objectives of this study and the research questions raised, the following null hypotheses were formulated for the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between financial audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between compliance audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between Performance audit and financial accountability of federal government ministries in Nigeria.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

The Concept of Public Sector Audit

Public-sector auditing can be described as a systematic process of objectively obtaining and evaluating evidence in public sector organizations to determine whether information or actual conditions conform to established criteria.

Gekula and Isanzu (2020) state that a public sector audit is the audit of the public sector's performance that covers specific financial operations and all government activities, both organizational and administrative systems.

Ebimobowei et al (2020) noted that public sector auditing entails the examination of public sector entities financial and non-financial reports that are required to have audited. It is done to ensure that adequate financial records are maintained to form the basis of public stewardship of public funds; proper accountability; prevent embezzlement of public funds; compliance and proper standards of conduct and assist public sector entities achieve value for money (Appah & Zibaghafa; 2018).

Financial Audit

Attah (2000), Is the type of audit that is conducted in order to ensure that the accounting and financial control systems are efficient and operating properly; and that financial transactions have been correctly authorized and accounted for. In other words, it is to ensure that the financial statements and accounts have been prepared to present a true and fair view of the state of affairs of the establishment concerned and in respect of the period covered by the audit. This is the type of audit conducted on the treasury accounts of the federation from time to time.

Compliance Audit

According to Stephen (2002), compliance audit deals with the responsibility of the organization to audit whether the activities of the company are in accordance with the relevant laws, regulations and authorities that govern the company. This involves reporting on the degree to which the audited entity is accountable for its actions and exercises good public governance. More specifically, these elements may involve auditing to what extent the audited entity follows rules, laws and regulation, budgetary resolutions, policy, established codes, or agreed upon terms, such as the terms of a contract or terms of a funding agreement.

Performance Audit

Focuses on whether organizations, programmes and institutions are performing in accordance with the principles of economy, efficiency and effectiveness and whether there is room for improvement. Performance is examined against suitable criteria, and the causes of deviations from those criteria or other problems are analyzed (Attah, 2000). The aim is to answer key audit questions and to provide recommendations for improvement.

Conversely, performance audits may also identify what is working well within audited entities or measure how performance has improved due to certain changes the entities have made to policy or operations (Lindaberg, 2020).

Concept of Accountability

According to Adesola (2019) accountability is one of those terms employed in government studies, which suffers from frequent misuse and imprecise or varying meaning.

Accountability is a fundamental principle in governance, education, and organizational management Imolong et al (2025). It ensures that individuals and institutions are held responsible for their actions, promoting transparency, efficiency, and ethical conduct, which ultimately enhances trust and performance in society. In education, accountability has become increasingly crucial in addressing the social contract between society and higher education institutions. It encompasses responsibility and answerability,

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requiring individuals to justify their actions and decisions to achieve desired objectives. Being accountable means taking responsibility for one's actions, omissions, and judgments while remaining open to corrections, consequences, or recognition.

Financial Accountability

Financial accountability is the obligation of any one handling resources, public office or any other positions of trust to report on the intended and actual use of the resources or of the designated office. The people given responsibility to manage the money need to be able to show that they are being good stewards of what is entrusted to them. It is important that they are protected from being tempted to use the money for their own purposes. In many countries there are laws that encourage good financial accountability, but the laws are not always obeyed. With smaller amounts of money it can be easy for accountability to be ignored. Yet financial accountability mechanisms can be easy to set up (Adegite, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Review

Contingency theory

Contingency theory is a method which study organizational behavior in which reasons are given as to how contingent factors such as technology, culture and the external environment affect the design and function of organizations. Hayes (1977) identifies the use of contingency theory in the studies of organizational assessment and subunit

evaluation where three major contingencies factors are affecting the sub-unit performances which are internal factors, interdependency factors and environmental factor. However, the viewpoint that is being assessed in this paper is the contingency theory and agency theory as the thought of accountability is most often portray in terms of principals and agents association.

Inspired Confidence Theory: This theory suggests that the primary function of the audit is to add credibility to the financial statements. The user's confidence is increased upon relying on audited financial statements rather than the financial statements presented by the management. The management therefore uses the audited financial statements to enhance stakeholder's faith in their managerial performance. Lending credibility theory is used by the management on the firm's audited financial statements to assure the stakeholder's of quality in management's leadership. In this view, the service that the auditors are selling to the clients is credibility (Watts, 2010). The theory helps the study to explore or to explain the auditor's report in order to comment on how accurately the bank presents its financial situation and how it is performing. This should support the shareholders that their investment is secured and also help to reduce the practice of misleading accounting procedures designed to show the company in a more favorable light. Essentially, the internal audit is represented as a process designed to evaluate the credibility of

information of a bank's financial statements (Hayes et al, 2015).

Empirical review

Owolabi and Ogunode (2020) examined public sector engagements, from the perspective of value for money audit. The research approach adopted for the study was content analysis. The study revealed that if properly carried out, value for money audit has the capacity to enhance reduction in costs of governance, misappropriation and theft of public fund, assist government in redirecting scarce public resources to priority areas and restore public confidence in the management of national economies. Public sector engagements and establishments are advised to instill the culture of regular value for money audit in all public sector institutions to ensure protection and proper utilization of public fund.

Ebimobowei et al (2020), investigated the effects of public sector audit, good governance and financial transparency on financial accountability of twenty – six (26) ministries in the Rivers State Civil Service. The study employed cross sectional survey research design. The population consisted of twenty – eight ministries and the Taro Yamene model was used for sample size determination while simple random sampling was employed. The study used primary and secondary sources of data collection. Questionnaire was the primary source of data collections after the application of

content and face validity while Cronbach alpha was employed to test the reliability of the instrument. The dependent variable was financial accountability index while the independent variables consisted of financial audit index, performance audit index, compliance audit index, good governance index and financial transparency index. The responses obtained from the questionnaire were analysed with univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. The multiple regression analysis suggested that there is a positive and significant relationship between financial audit index, performance audit index, compliance audit index, good governance index and financial transparency index on accountability in public sectors in Rivers State. The study concluded that public sector audit, good governance and financial transparency promote financial accountability in the Nigerian public sector. Therefore, the following recommendations were provided amongst others that The Accounting Officers in government Ministries, Department and Agencies (MDA) should carry out government business in accordance with accountability, transparency, effectiveness and efficiency, responsiveness, forward vision and rule of law for the welfare of the citizens.

3. Methodology

This study employed a **survey research design** to systematically collect and analyze data from respondents in order to examine the relationship between public sector audit and

accountability in Nigerian federal ministries. The population consisted of twenty-six (26) federal ministries, and the respondents were seventy-eight (78) officials comprising permanent secretaries, chief accountants, and internal auditors. Given the manageable population size, a **census approach** was adopted, ensuring that the entire population was included in the study. Data were collected primarily through a structured questionnaire titled Public Sector Audit and Accountability Questionnaire (PSAAQ), which was divided into two sections: Section A (respondents’ demographic information) and Section B (items on financial audit, compliance audit, performance audit, and accountability). A five-point Likert scale was used to measure the responses. To ensure validity, the instrument was subjected to expert review, while reliability was confirmed through a pilot test using Cronbach’s alpha coefficient. Questionnaires were administered through both personal visits and mail, with the assistance of

trained research aides. Data generated were analyzed using both **descriptive statistics** (frequencies and mean scores) for respondent characteristics and research questions, and **inferential statistics** (Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Ordinary Least Squares regression) for hypothesis testing at a 5% significance level. The analyses were conducted with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 23).

Questionnaire Administration and Retrieval

Out of the seventy-eight (78) questionnaires administered, sixty-five (65), representing 83.33%, were duly completed and found usable for analysis. Ten (10) questionnaires, accounting for 12.82%, were not returned, while three (3), representing 3.85%, were returned but deemed invalid. Accordingly, a total of sixty-five (65) valid responses formed the basis of the analysis, as presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Questionnaire Administration and Retrieval

	Frequencies	Percentages
Number of questionnaire returned and usable	65	83.33%
Number of questionnaire non-returnable	10	12.82%
Number of questionnaire returned and not usable	3	3.85%
Total	78	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2022.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents The demographic profile of respondents is a critical component of research reporting, as it

provides valuable context for understanding the characteristics of the study population and enhances the credibility and applicability of the findings. In this study, the demographic

distribution of participants was examined, beginning with gender, which is summarized in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequencies	Percentages
Male	42	64.62%
Female	23	35.38%
Total	65	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

The data in Table 4.2 reveal that 42 respondents (64.62%) were male, while 23 respondents (35.38%) were female, indicating that the majority of participants in the study were male. This suggests that male employees constitute a

larger proportion of the workforce in the ministries surveyed. Furthermore, the marital status of respondents is presented in Table 4.3, providing additional demographic insights into the study population

Table 4.3: Marital Status of Respondents

Status	Frequencies	Percentages
Single	16	24.62%
Married	33	50.77%
Divorced	10	15.38%
Widowed	6	9.23%
Total	65	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

As shown in Table 4.3, the marital status distribution of respondents indicates that 16 (24.62%) were single, 33 (50.77%) were married, 10 (15.38%) were divorced, and 6 (9.23%) were widowed. This reveals that the majority of respondents were married, suggesting that most participants had family responsibilities that

could potentially influence their perspectives on financial accountability and workplace practices. The age distribution of respondents is further presented in Table 4.4, providing deeper insights into the demographic characteristics of the study population.

Table 4.4: Age of Respondents

Age	Frequencies	Percentages
20 and Below	4	6.15%
21-30	19	29.23%
31-40	20	30.77%
41-Above	22	33.85%
Total	65	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 4.4 presents the age distribution of respondents, showing that 4 (6.15%) were aged 20 years and below, 19 (29.23%) fell within 21–30 years, 20 (30.77%) were within 31–40 years, and 22 (33.85%) were 41 years and above. The results indicate that the largest proportion of respondents were aged 41 years and above, suggesting that the study sample was dominated by relatively older and more experienced individuals who are likely to possess deeper insights into public sector operations and accountability practices. Further details on the educational background of respondents are presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Educational Background of Respondents

Qualification	Frequencies	Percentages
NCE/Diploma	0	0.00%
HND/B.Sc	21	32.31%
MBA/M.Sc/MA	35	53.85%
Others	9	13.84%
Total	65	100%

Source: Survey Data, 2023.

Table 4.5 shows the educational qualifications of respondents, revealing that none held an NCE/Diploma, 21 (32.31%) possessed HND/B.Sc. degrees, 35 (53.85%) had MBA/M.Sc./MA qualifications, and 9 (13.84%) obtained other advanced degrees. This indicates that the majority of respondents were postgraduate degree holders, suggesting a relatively well-educated workforce within the ministries. Such a high level of educational attainment implies that the respondents are likely to possess the requisite knowledge and analytical capacity to provide informed perspectives on issues of public sector audit and accountability

Univariate Analysis

This section presents the descriptive results of both the dependent and independent variables employed in the study. Specifically, the focus is on financial accountability in Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria. To measure this construct, five test items were developed and assessed using a modified five-point Likert scale ranging from *strongly agree* (5) to *undecided* (1). The responses were analyzed to determine the extent of financial accountability practices within the ministries, and the summarized results are presented in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Descriptive Analysis of Financial Accountability in Nigeria

S/N	Assertions on Financial Accountability	SA(5)	A(4)	I(3)	D(2)	SD(1)	Total	Mean
1.	The roles and responsibilities of the parties in accountability relationship are well understood and effective	11 (55)	16 (64)	8 (24)	12(24)	18(18)	65(185)	2.85
2.	The performance expectations are clearly linked to and in balance with authorities, skills, and resources of each party	15(75)	10(40)	2(6)	20(40)	18(18)	65(179)	2.75
3.	The accounting report is seen as credible, timely, and it describes the results accomplished, resources and actions taken in light of the agreed expectations	10(50)	20(80)	0(0)	15(30)	20(20)	65(180)	2.77
4.	A reasonable review, adjustment and feedback on the performance achieved is usually conducted by the party that is accountable	4(20)	5(20)	1(3)	21(42)	34(34)	65(119)	1.83
5.	Financial administration tasks are carried out by more than one person to reduce error or fraud	11(55)	20(80)	3(9)	16(32)	15(15)	65(191)	2.94
	Average							2.63

Source: Survey Data, 2022

The results presented in Table 4.6 show that the overall mean score for financial accountability in Federal Government Ministries is 2.63, which falls below the benchmark value of 3.0 on a five-point Likert scale. This indicates that financial accountability within the ministries is generally weak. Specifically, the analysis reveals several critical shortcomings: the roles and responsibilities of parties in accountability relationships are neither clearly understood nor effectively implemented; performance expectations are poorly aligned with available authority, skills, and resources; accounting reports are widely perceived as lacking credibility, timeliness, and comprehensive detail; systematic review, adjustment, and feedback on performance are seldom undertaken; and financial administration tasks are rarely segregated among multiple individuals, thereby increasing the risk of error and fraud. These findings underscore significant gaps in accountability structures and practices, which undermine transparency, efficiency, and effective stewardship of public resources in Nigeria’s federal ministries.

Financial Audit

Table 4.7: Descriptive Analysis of Financial Audit in Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

S/N	Assertions on Financial Audit	SA (5)	A (4)	I (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
1	Testing the existence and effectiveness of management controls that prevent financial statement misstatement	14 (70)	26 (104)	0 (0)	13 (26)	12 (12)	65 (212)	3.26
2	Tracing financial records of subsequent periods	20 (100)	10 (40)	8 (24)	11 (22)	16 (16)	65 (202)	3.11
3	Physical examination and counting of inventory items	13 (65)	13 (52)	13 (39)	13 (26)	13 (13)	65 (195)	3.00
4	Regular checking of the postings previously made	15 (75)	11 (44)	5 (15)	20 (40)	14 (14)	65 (188)	2.89
5	Verification of existence, ownership, title, and value of assets and determination of the extent and nature of liabilities	12 (60)	13 (52)	12 (36)	15 (30)	13 (13)	65 (191)	2.94
Average							3.00	

Source: Survey Data, 2023

Note: Figures in brackets are weighted frequencies

The results in Table 4.7 indicate that the overall mean score of financial audit in federal government ministries is 3.00, which corresponds with the benchmark value of 3.0 on the five-point Likert scale. This suggests that the state of financial auditing practices in the ministries is moderate—neither robust nor particularly weak. A closer examination of the individual items reveals areas of strength and concern. Specifically, there is reasonable evidence that management controls aimed at preventing financial statement misstatements are being tested (mean = 3.26), and financial records of subsequent periods are traced (mean = 3.11). Similarly, physical examination and counting of inventory items are carried out, though only at a moderate level (mean = 3.00). However, significant weaknesses exist in routine audit procedures: regular checking of previous postings is not consistently undertaken (mean = 2.89), and verification of assets and liabilities in terms of ownership, title, and valuation is inadequately addressed (mean = 2.94). Taken together, these findings highlight that while some core audit functions are operational, lapses in critical areas such as asset verification and ongoing postings review undermine the overall effectiveness and reliability of financial audits in federal government ministries.

Compliance Audit

Table 4.8: Descriptive Analysis of Compliance Audit in Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

S/N	Assertions on Compliance Audit	SA (5)	A (4)	I (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
1	Audit reports evaluate the strength and thoroughness of compliance preparations, security policies, user access controls, and risk management procedures over the course of a compliance audit	15 (75)	15 (60)	7 (21)	18 (36)	10 (10)	65 (202)	3.11
2	Financial transactions and information are, in all material respects, in compliance with the authorities which govern the audited entity	16 (80)	16 (64)	1 (3)	16 (32)	16 (16)	65 (195)	3.00
3	Adherence to formal criteria such as relevant laws, regulations, and agreements in the auditing process	10 (50)	13 (52)	4 (12)	23 (46)	15 (15)	65 (175)	2.69
4	Authorities are relevant acts or resolutions of the legislature or other statutory instruments, directions, and guidance issued by public sector bodies with powers	17 (85)	14 (56)	4 (12)	14 (28)	16 (16)	65 (197)	3.03

S/N	Assertions on Compliance Audit	SA (5)	A (4)	I (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
	provided in statute, with which the audited entity is expected to comply							
5	The need exists to perform procedures that reduce or manage the risk of reaching inappropriate conclusions and provide credible information to intended users so that they may make informed decisions	14 (70)	11 (44)	5 (15)	20 (60)	15 (15)	65 (184)	2.83
	Average							2.93

Source: Survey Data, 2023

Note: Figures in brackets are weighted frequencies

The results in Table 4.8 reveal that the overall mean score of compliance audit in federal government ministries is 2.93, which falls below the benchmark value of 3.0 on the five-point Likert scale. This suggests that compliance audit practices in the ministries are generally weak, raising concerns about adherence to statutory regulations and effective oversight. A closer look at the mean scores shows that while audit reports moderately evaluate compliance processes such as risk management, security policies, and user access controls (mean = 3.11), and financial transactions are somewhat aligned with governing authorities (mean = 3.00), critical gaps persist. Notably, there is poor adherence to formal criteria such as laws, regulations, and agreements during audits (mean = 2.69), and inadequate verification of compliance with statutory instruments and directives (mean = 3.03). Furthermore, the lack of emphasis on implementing audit procedures to mitigate risks of inaccurate conclusions and to ensure reliable reporting (mean = 2.83) further weakens compliance assurance. Collectively, these findings highlight deficiencies in compliance auditing that undermine transparency, weaken institutional accountability, and expose the ministries to operational and reputational risks.

Performance Audit

Table 4.9: Descriptive Analysis of Performance Audit in Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

S/N	Assertions on Performance Audit	SA (5)	A (4)	I (3)	D (2)	SD (1)	Total	Mean
1	Testing whether a government is making good use of resources to effectively deliver its policy goals and achieve its intended impact	6 (30)	19 (76)	5 (15)	15 (30)	20 (20)	65 (171)	2.63
2	Identifying what is working well within audited entities or measuring how performance has improved due to certain changes the entities have made to policy or operations	23 (115)	15 (60)	3 (9)	9 (18)	15 (15)	65 (217)	3.34
3	The resources used are available in due time, of appropriate quantity and quality, and at the best price	12 (60)	13 (52)	12 (36)	10 (20)	18 (18)	65 (186)	3.04
4	Inputs have been put to optimal and satisfactory use, and the same or similar outputs (in terms of quantity, quality and turnaround time) have been achieved with fewer resources	13 (65)	13 (52)	13 (39)	13 (26)	13 (13)	65 (195)	3.00
5	The extent to which policy objectives have been met in terms of the generated output is high	21 (105)	17 (68)	3 (9)	14 (28)	10 (10)	65 (220)	3.38
Average								3.08

Source: Survey Data, 2023

Note: Figures in brackets are weighted frequencies

The results presented in Table 4.9 indicate that the overall mean score for performance audit in federal government ministries is 3.08, which slightly exceeds the benchmark value of 3.0 on the five-point Likert scale. This suggests that performance audit practices in the ministries are moderately effective. Specifically, the findings reveal weaknesses in assessing whether government resources are optimally used to deliver policy goals and achieve intended impacts (mean = 2.63), indicating inefficiencies in aligning resources with outcomes. However, stronger performance is recorded in identifying areas of improvement within audited entities (mean = 3.34) and assessing the extent to which policy objectives are achieved through outputs (mean = 3.38). Similarly, resource availability and quality were rated just

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above the benchmark (mean = 3.04), while the efficiency of input utilization achieved only a marginal score (mean = 3.00). Overall, while the evidence points to some progress in performance auditing, the results suggest only a moderate level of effectiveness rather than a high standard, reflecting persistent gaps in resource optimization, policy impact evaluation, and sustainable accountability in federal government ministries.

Bivariate Analysis

Table 4.10: Relationship between Financial Audit (FIA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) of Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

FIA	FAC
FIA Pearson Correlation = 1.000	.913
Sig. (2-tailed) = —	.000
N = 65	N = 65
FAC Pearson Correlation = .913	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed) = .000	—
N = 65	N = 65

Source: SPSS Version 23 Window Output

The correlation analysis presented in Table 4.10 shows a strong positive relationship between financial audit (FIA) and financial accountability (FAC) in federal government ministries, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of **0.913**, which is very close to +1. This indicates that improvements in financial audit practices are strongly associated with higher levels of financial accountability. Furthermore, the p-value of **0.000**, which is below the 0.05 level of significance, confirms that this relationship is statistically significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H₀₁), which states that there is no significant relationship between financial audit and financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria, is rejected. This finding underscores the critical role of robust financial audit mechanisms in fostering accountability and transparency within Nigeria's public sector.

Compliance Audit and Financial Accountability

Table 4.11: Compliance Audit (COA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) of Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

COA	FAC
COA Pearson Correlation = 1.000	.247
Sig. (2-tailed) = —	.082
N = 65	N = 65
FAC Pearson Correlation = .247	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed) = .096	—
N = 65	N = 65

Source: SPSS Version 23 Window Output

The correlation results in Table 4.11 reveal a Pearson correlation coefficient of **0.247** between compliance audit (COA) and financial accountability (FAC) in federal government ministries, indicating only a weak positive association between the two variables. However, the significance value of **0.082**, which is above the 0.05 threshold, shows that this relationship is not statistically significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis (Ho2), which posits that there is no significant relationship between compliance audit and financial accountability in federal government ministries, is accepted. This finding implies that compliance audits, as currently implemented, do not exert a meaningful influence on financial accountability within Nigeria’s public sector. It further suggests possible weaknesses in adherence to regulatory frameworks, enforcement mechanisms, or the practical execution of compliance audits, which may limit their effectiveness in strengthening accountability.

Performance Audit and Financial Accountability

Table 4.12: Performance Audit (PEA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) of Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

PEA	FAC
PEA Pearson Correlation = 1.000	.139
Sig. (2-tailed) = —	.214
N = 65	N = 65
FAC Pearson Correlation = .139	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed) = .214	—
N = 65	N = 65

Source: SPSS Version 23 Window Output

The result presented in Table 4.12 shows a Pearson correlation coefficient of **0.139** between performance audit (PEA) and financial accountability (FAC) in federal government ministries, which indicates a weak positive association between the two variables. However, the significance value of **0.214**, which is greater than the 0.05 level, demonstrates that the relationship is not statistically significant. Based on this outcome, the null hypothesis is accepted, confirming that performance audit has no significant effect on financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria. This suggests that, despite the presence of performance audits, their implementation has not been strong enough to drive meaningful improvements in accountability practices. The finding points to possible limitations in how performance audits are designed, executed, or enforced, thereby reducing their impact on

ensuring transparency, efficiency, and responsible use of public resources.

Summary of Findings

The findings of this study reveal that the effectiveness of audits in promoting accountability within federal ministries in Nigeria varies considerably across audit types. Specifically, financial audits were found to have a significant and positive influence on financial accountability, underscoring their central role as a reliable mechanism for ensuring transparency and proper stewardship of public resources. In contrast, compliance audits demonstrated only a weak and statistically insignificant effect, suggesting limitations in their design or enforcement. Similarly, while performance audits exhibited a marginally stronger descriptive relationship with accountability, the effect was not statistically significant, indicating insufficient impact in practice. Collectively, these results suggest that although audits are routinely

undertaken in federal ministries, their ability to foster accountability is contingent upon the audit type, with financial audits being the most effective. To enhance accountability, compliance and performance audits must be strengthened in terms of scope, methodological rigor, and enforcement to serve as credible instruments of public sector governance.

Discussion of Findings

Financial audit (FIA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) of Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria.

The test of hypotheses one (H_{01}), found that there is a positive strong relationship between financial audit (FIA) and financial accountability (FAC) as shown in table 4.12 with the correlation coefficient value of $r = 0.913^{**}$ significant at $p = 0.00 < 0.05$. Hence, the conclusion that there is a significant relationship between financial audit (FIA) and financial accountability (FAC). This finding is in line with the study of this is in consonant with the study of Ozuomba (2019) investigated performance audit and accountability of public sector entities in Nigeria.

Compliance audit (COA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) of Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

The test of hypotheses four (H_{04}), found that there is a positive weak relationship between compliance audit (COA) and financial accountability (FAC) as shown in table 4.15 with the correlation coefficient value of $r = 0.247^{**}$ significant at $p = 0.00 < 0.05$. Hence, the

conclusion that there is a significant relationship between compliance audit (COA) and financial accountability (FAC). The result is in line with the study of Mohammed, Unuigbokhai, & Ihimekpen (2019) investigated the role of internal audit in strengthening corporate governance in Nigeria.

Performance audit (PEA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) of Federal Government Ministries in Nigeria

The test of hypotheses seven (H_{07}), found that there is a positive relationship between Performance Audit (PEA) and Financial Accountability (FAC) as shown in table 4.18 with the correlation coefficient value of $r = 0.139^{**}$ significant at $p = 0.00 < 0.05$. Hence the conclusions that there is a significant relationship between audit committee and return on equity and also that performance audit statistically affect financial accountability. The implication of the findings is in line with According to Ssenyondo, (2020) in his research work of Financial Controls and Accountability in the Public Sector, the research was carried out using correlation and descriptive research design to easily and clearly establish the relationship between the variables.

Summary

Accountability in public sector all through the world is being giving genuine consideration in perspective on the way that administration is the most astounding high-roller of open store. The general public is increasingly requiring public

office holders to be more accountable by a demonstration of effective use of public assets and funds in the delivery of administrations and quest for government targets. Due to an increasing public demands for transparency in governance and the global outcry against corruption in recent times, accountability has now become of serious worry in numerous nations including Nigeria. This lack of transparency and accountability of funds in the public sector can be minimized through effective and efficient auditing of government accounts and records called public sector audit.

To generate the data necessary for this study, the survey research design was adopted and the population comprises twenty-six (26) federal ministries but seventy-eight (87) respondents comprising the permanent secretary, chief accountant, and the internal auditor of various federal ministries in Nigeria. The data were collected through a questionnaire designed in modified 5 point Likert scale. The generated data were analyzed descriptively using frequencies, and mean scores while the stated hypotheses were statistically tested with the Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of correlation and ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique. After which interpretation of the results was made.

The findings generated from this study are as follows:

(i) The mean score of financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria is 2.63, which is less than the

beach mark of 3.0 on a five-point Likert scale. This implies that financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria is low.

(ii) The mean score of financial audit in federal government ministries in Nigeria is 3.00, which is equivalent to the beach mark of 3.0 on a five-point Likert scale. This implies that financial audit in federal government ministries in Nigeria is moderate.

(iii) The mean score of the application of auditing standards in federal government ministries in Nigeria is 2.66, which is less than the beach mark of 3.0 on a five-point Likert scale. This implies that the application of auditing standards in federal government ministries in Nigeria is low.

(iv) The correlation co-efficient (0.913) and the p-value (0.000) indicate a significant relationship between financial audit and financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria.

(v) The correlation coefficient (0.247) and the p-value (0.082) indicate an insignificant relationship between compliance audit and financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria.

(vi) The correlation coefficient (0.139) and the p-value (0.214) indicate an insignificant relationship between performance audit

and financial accountability in federal government ministries in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Public office is a sacred trust, and those entrusted with public resources have a duty to ensure their prudent management, transparent allocation, and efficient utilization for the benefit of citizens. Accountability in the public sector entails not only rendering accurate accounts but also being held responsible for outcomes, thereby ensuring that public funds are spent economically, wastage and misuse are minimized, and society derives value from public expenditure. In democratic settings, accountability empowers citizens to monitor government actions, prevent abuse of power, and promote efficiency, effectiveness, and transparency in governance. In Nigeria, the lack of accountability in managing public funds can be mitigated through effective auditing, which provides credibility to financial reports, strengthens internal controls, reduces inefficiencies, and safeguards public assets. This study therefore concludes that a well-conducted public sector audit significantly enhances accountability, reduces governance costs, redirects scarce resources to priority needs, and restores public confidence in the management of the national economy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings generated from this study and the conclusion drawn there from, the following recommendations were made:

- (i) There should be persistent use of financial audit, compliance audit and performance audit in federal government ministries to ensure public accountability.
- (ii) The government should employ more qualified audit personnel and equipped them with necessary working materials, training so that they can improve their efficiency.
- (iii) Staff of government audit department should avoid informing the ministries and other public sector institutions of their visit ahead of time, which give sufficient time for covering up of any irregularity that the auditor may otherwise have noticed in the course of the audit work.

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